

Uploading specimen images via OpenRefine into Wikimedia Commons

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[Brachyglottis huntii](#) (CHR 602367). Allan Herbarium, New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute. [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons.

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Introduction

This documentation is intended to guide the staff of the Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research group (MWLR group) of the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute (NZBSI) as well as other Wikimedia Commons (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Main_Page) editors in the bulk uploading of natural history specimen images into Wikimedia Commons via OpenRefine (<https://openrefine.org/>).

This documentation will outline a workflow used by the writer in late 2025 / early 2026 and is reliant on tools used to edit Wikimedia Commons such as Pattypan and OpenRefine as at those dates.

Wiki community guidance

For more general information on uploading images into Wikimedia Commons via OpenRefine please refer to Wikimedia Commons documentation set out here https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:OpenRefine/Uploading_files_with_OpenRefine.

Wiki upload tools

For single image or small batch uploads of openly licensed or public domain images see https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Upload_Wizard

For an alternative tool for batch uploads of files to Wikimedia Commons that requires lower technical skills than OpenRefine see Pattypan <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Pattypan>.

Data model for specimen image uploads

This documentation will use the *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400> to help inform this work. See also the *Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikimedia Commons + SDC* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881782> which provides a crosswalk between the [Darwin Core](#) data standard and the above mentioned *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images*.

At the time of writing, this data model has not yet been utilised to create or edit existing Wikimedia Commons templates, particularly the `{{Specimen}}` template, although this is expected to feature in future work.

As a result, this documentation will outline the use of the `{{Information}}` template to generate the needed Wikimedia Commons file Information page. The future development of the `{{Specimen}}` template is anticipated. This proposed future development will likely ensure first, that the `{{Specimen}}` template complies with the above data model and second, that the template is [Lua](#) compliant. Lua is a programming language that can be embedded into Wikimedia Commons templates to empower them to pull the data needed for that template from the structured data added to the Wikimedia Commons image file.

This workflow will therefore outline the appropriate structured data statements needed to be added to specimen image files in Wikimedia Commons both to empower the likely improved {{Specimen}} template and also to comply with the best practice given in the above mentioned data model.

Guidance for MWLR group employees uploading images

Further guidance for employees of the MWLR group wanting to upload New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute images into Wikimedia Commons is provided in the publication *Wikimedia Commons uploads : Uploading of images by an employee of the copyright holder* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556>.

Other helpful information can be found on the Wikimedia Commons page for uploading works by a third party https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Uploading_works_by_a_third_party.

The process outlined below is easier if the specimen images already have an existing digital presence (for example on GBIF.org) and are openly licensed on those relevant websites. If the specimen images to be uploaded to Wikimedia Commons do not yet have a digital presence, the uploader should follow the advice given in both the above linked resources.

Are the images suitable for Wikimedia Commons?

Before uploading specimen images into Wikimedia Commons, the uploader should consider whether those images hurdle two requirements. The first requirement is whether the images are either [freely licensed](#) or in the [public domain](#). For further information on Wikimedia Commons requirements see https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:First_steps/Contributing.

Freely licensed images

There are multiple different types of copyright license that can guide the reuse of copyrighted works. Wikimedia Commons allows only freely licensed images to be uploaded onto its platform. The most commonly used copyright licences are those of the international non profit organisation, Creative Commons (<https://creativecommons.org/>).

An image falls within the category of “freely licensed” for the purposes of Wikimedia Commons, if its reuse has been licensed under the Creative Commons **CC0** (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0>), **CC BY** (for example <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), or **CC BY-SA** (for example <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>) licences.

Public domain images

An image can also be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons if it has ascended to the public domain. When considering the public domain for the purposes of an upload to Wikimedia Commons, the image should be in the public domain in the United States, in the public domain in the country the uploader is working in, **AND** in the public domain in the source country from which the image originates. Guidance should be sought if the uploader is unsure of whether an image is in the public domain of these three jurisdictions. See https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Help:Public_domain for more information.

Are the images educational?

The second requirement is that the images must be **educational**. This is a requirement of the official policy of Wikimedia Commons https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Project_scope. The expression "educational" is to be understood according to its broad meaning of "providing knowledge; instructional or informative". It is recommended that any uploader of files to Wikimedia Commons read the project's policy on Project scope if they are uncertain as to whether the images they wish to upload are educational.

Can the Editor upload to Wikimedia Commons?

Account

The editor will need to have a Wikipedia or Wikimedia Commons registered account to upload files to Wikimedia Commons. Potential editors can register at the "Log in / create account" link in the upper right corner of the main Wikimedia Commons page https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Main_Page. Alternatively, use this link to register <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Special:UserLogin>. The uploader should enter a user name for their account and also create a password for that account. It is recommended that the user name and password is noted down by the new editor for future reference.

If the editor already has [an account on Wikipedia or any other Wikimedia project](#), they are already signed up at Wikimedia Commons and should use those log in details to ensure they are logged into the Wikimedia Commons platform.

Familiarity with Wikimedia Commons

Prior to bulk uploading images to Wikimedia Commons, it is recommended that the uploader become familiar with Wikimedia Commons platform. The uploader should have not just a Wikimedia Commons account but also have reached autoconfirmed status https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Autoconfirmed_users, have created a User page https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:User_pages to assist with community engagement and have uploaded files via the more manual Wikimedia Commons upload wizard https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Upload_Wizard to familiarise themselves with the Wikimedia Commons platform.

User preferences

It is also recommended that the uploader adjust their account user preferences to allow email notifications for when other editors post on the uploader's talk page. Editors can do this by clicking this link

<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Special:Preferences#mw-prefsection-echo> and adjusting their preferences. This will help ensure any community engagement regarding uploads reaches the uploader.

Access to image files

The editor should have access to the image files intended to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons. The image files will need to be on a computer or device that is accessible by the uploader.

Maximum file size

Information on the maximum file size that Wikimedia Commons will accept can be found here https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Maximum_file_size.

Can the editor use OpenRefine to bulk upload?

It is recommended that the uploader have at least a basic knowledge of OpenRefine.

Information on training resources can be found at

<https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/OpenRefine/Training>.

If the editor is unfamiliar with OpenRefine, the Wikimedia Commons upload tool [Pattypan](#) is recommended as a less technically challenging tool for the uploader to use. However Pattypan offers only a limited number of Wikimedia Commons templates. As at the date of publication, the most suitable template available in Pattypan for specimen images would be the basic Wikimedia Commons `{{Information}}` template. Pattypan also does not upload structured data about the file into Wikimedia Commons.

OpenRefine limitations

OpenRefine also has limitations. It is a more complex tool compared to Pattypan. However OpenRefine can support the upload of all kinds of media files into Wikimedia Commons. But, like many upload tools, OpenRefine can have trouble uploading Tagged Image File Format (TIFF) files.

The advantage of OpenRefine is that it empowers the upload of comprehensive structured data ensuring the greater discoverability of image files in Wikimedia Commons. For batch uploading to Wikimedia Commons via OpenRefine, the uploader will need to install OpenRefine 3.7 or newer.

OpenRefine supports the uploading of local files up to 100MB. It is possible to upload larger files from a URL. For more information see <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:OpenRefine>. However the uploader should again be cognizant of Wikimedia Commons guidance on maximum file size https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Maximum_file_size.

Installing OpenRefine

Install OpenRefine on the computer upon which the images files needing to be uploaded are stored. Editors can do this by downloading OpenRefine from this link <https://openrefine.org/download.html> and installing it on the relevant computer.

OpenRefine provides detailed instructions in its user manual for the installation and running of OpenRefine <https://openrefine.org/docs>.

Wikimedia Commons reconciliation service

In order to ensure the Wikimedia Commons reconciliation service is added to OpenRefine the uploader should create a project.

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Then on the top righthand side of that project, select the dropdown menu for “Extensions Wikibase”. Then select “Manage Wikibase instances...”.

Manage Wikibase instances

Click on an item below to select it as the target Wikibase to work against. This will clear any existing schema. After switching to the target Wikibase, you should reconcile your data against it before editing the schema.

Wikidata Delete
<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/>

Wikimedia Commons **active**
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/>

Add Wikibase Discover Wikibase instances... OK Cancel

Screenshot of an OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Select and add the Wikimedia Commons Wikibase instance. If the Wikimedia Commons Wikibase is not listed, press the “Discover Wikibase instances...” and search for it in order to select it. Then press “OK” at the bottom right of the popup box.

Wikimedia Commons extension to OpenRefine

The uploader should, if possible, also ensure the Wikimedia Commons extension to OpenRefine is downloaded and installed <https://github.com/OpenRefine/CommonsExtension>. The github repository also provides guidance on the installation <https://github.com/OpenRefine/CommonsExtension#install-this-extension-in-openrefine>.

This extension can assist with the editing or enriching of the structured data attached to the uploaded files after initial upload.

Files extension to OpenRefine

The uploader should, if possible, also ensure the Files extension to OpenRefine is downloaded and installed <https://github.com/OpenRefine/FilesExtension>.

This extension allows OpenRefine users to start an OpenRefine project by uploading details of files from folders on their local system. It also allows users to ensure the file metadata is added to that project. For further information see <https://openrefine.org/blog/2025/02/11/FilesExtension>.

Bulk Uploads with OpenRefine

Creating a File path for files to be uploaded

Further information on creating a file path for files to be uploaded via OpenRefine as well as instructions based on the type of operating system of the computer for this process can also be found here

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:OpenRefine/Uploading_files_with_OpenRefine#File_path_or_URL.

Using the Pattypan tool

If the uploader is unable to use the OpenRefine file extension, another option to assist with the generation of the needed list of image file path names is to use the Wikimedia Commons Pattypan tool <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Pattypan>. Pattypan can be used to generate a spreadsheet that can either be worked on prior to being imported into OpenRefine or can immediately be loaded into OpenRefine for further work.

In this workflow Pattypan is used mainly to ensure an appropriate list of file path names are generated in spreadsheet form. Although specimen image files can be uploaded via Pattypan, this tool does not add the all important structured data.

When using Pattypan to generate a spreadsheet of file path names for specimen images, it is recommended that the Wikimedia Commons [{{Information}}](#) template be used. This template will assist with ensuring the spreadsheet will contain the minimum required information needed for each image file upload.

The OpenRefine upload process documented here ensures the basic information template information is enhanced with detailed structured data attached to each image file.

How to use Pattypan to obtain file path names

Ensure the image files intended to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons are in a separate folder on the uploader's computer.

Download the Pattypan tool from via link <https://github.com/yarl/pattypan/releases> and activate the tool.

Screenshot of Pattypan main window. Pattypan software is licensed under the [Expat License](#), sometimes known as the MIT Licence. The screenshot taken by Siobhan Leachman is licensed [CC0](#).

Generate a spreadsheet by pressing the blue “Generate Spreadsheet” button and select the required image file folder on the computer hard drive.

Screenshot showing the selection of the folder containing the files needed to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons. Pattypan software is licensed under the [Expat License](#), sometimes known as the MIT Licence. The screenshot taken by Siobhan Leachman is licensed [CC0](#).

Once the required folder is selected press the “next” button the bottom righthand side of the tool.

At this step you can set the source of wikicode. You can choose between already created templates and writing wikicode by your own.

Field name	Yes / Const / No	Value
Description	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
Date	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Preload date from Exif
Source	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	
Author	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	Allan Herbarium
Permission	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	CC BY 4.0
Other versions	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input checked="" type="radio"/>	
License	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>	{{Cc-by-4.0}}

Screenshot showing the selection of the folder containing the files needed to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons. Pattypan software is licensed under the [Expat License](#), sometimes known as the MIT Licence. The screenshot taken by Siobhan Leachman is licensed [CC0](#).

Then select the `{{Information}}` template on the left hand side menu column. Begin to fill out the information boxes on the right hand side. The information to be added to these boxes should apply to all the files being uploaded. If each file requires an individual description or source then these boxes should be left blank and this data should be added in the OpenRefine project.

The licence box should be populated with the Wikitext for the appropriate Wikimedia Commons copyright licence template. See the following link to find the Wikitext for the Wikimedia Commons copyright license template needed https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Copyright_tags.

Then press the “next” button on the bottom right hand side of the tool.

Screenshot showing the final stage of creating a spreadsheet for an upload of images on Pattypan. Pattypan software is licensed under the [Expat License](#), sometimes known as the MIT Licence. The screenshot taken by Siobhan Leachman is licensed [CC0](#).

Pattypan will then provide the option to create the spreadsheet file. If required, rename the spreadsheet that will be generated and then press the blue “Create file” button. Pattypan will then generate an Excel spreadsheet with columns for each type of data needed for the chosen Wikimedia Commons template.

Once the file has been created the editor can press the “Open file” link underneath the “Create file” blue button to examine the file.

path	name	description	date	source	author	permission	licence	categories
/Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	Carex comans (CHR 691423)				Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0	{{Cc-by-4.0}}	
/Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png	Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901)				Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0	{{Cc-by-4.0}}	
/Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095)				Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0	{{Cc-by-4.0}}	

Screenshot of xls spreadsheet generated via Pattypan. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The file will show the file path name and the file name. Other columns generated in the spreadsheet will include columns for the source, author, permission, licence and a column for Wikimedia Commons categories. Whether there is content in these columns or not will depend on the data provided to Pattypan during the creation of the spreadsheet.

OpenRefine

This spreadsheet can now be added to OpenRefine and worked on in that tool to ensure the necessary information can be added both to the File information page as well as the Structured Data page for the image file in Wikimedia Commons.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project being prepared for creation. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To add the spreadsheet, open OpenRefine, press the “create project” tab and then select “This Computer”. Select the Pattypan generated xls file from the folder in which the images to be uploaded are stored.

Screenshot of OpenRefine project being prepared for creation with the Pattypan xls file being imported. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Check the OpenRefine project to ensure the file is properly uploaded, rename the project if appropriate, then press “Create project”.

Then begin working on the OpenRefine project ensuring the necessary data is added and is appropriately prepared before uploading the image files into Wikimedia Commons. General guidance on the quality and description of files to be donated to Wikimedia Commons can be found at this page

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:First_steps/Quality_and_description.

The aim of the documentation is to provide both sufficient data to ensure the “File information” Wikimedia Commons page is generated with at least the minimum required information and also to ensure the structured data attached to the files are sufficient to ensure the files can be easily queried for, found and reused.

Again, this documentation recommends the addition of comprehensive structured data to each specimen image file uploaded in line with the best practice documentation *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400>.

Recommended first practical step

As the editor will be adding columns to the OpenRefine project to populate with appropriate data for each file, it is recommended that a blank column be created in the OpenRefine project to assist with the creation of these columns.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Go to any column in OpenRefine, select the dropdown menu and create a column using the “add column based on this column...” selection.

Add column based on column blank

New column name

On error set to blank store error copy value from original column

Expression Language No syntax error.

Preview History Starred Help

row	value	null
1.	null	null
2.	null	null
3.	null	null
4.	null	null
5.	null	null
6.	null	null

OK Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Title that column “blank column” or something similar and ensure the word “null” is typed in the GREL expression box.

This blank column can then be used to generate new columns to assist in adding the needed structured data to the image files when they are uploaded into Wikimedia Commons.

File information data

As explained in more detail above, at the writing of this documentation it is recommended that the `{{Information}}` Wikimedia Commons template be used. However this documentation anticipates that a detailed Lua module will be created to assist the `{{Specimen}}` Wikimedia Commons template to pull data from the structured data added to specimen image files and use that data to create the File information page for those images on Wikimedia Commons. As a result, this workflow encourages the addition of comprehensive structured data to an image file to support the future use of the `{{Specimen}}` template.

`{{Information}}` template

The information below sets out the statements and their associated data needed to generate the File information page for an image file in Wikimedia Commons using the Wikimedia Commons `{{Information}}` template.

[File information](#)
[Structured data](#)

Captions
[Edit](#)

English	Specimen of <i>Brachyglottis huntii</i> (CHR 602367) from the Allan herbarium, Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research
---------	---

Summary [\[edit \]](#)

Description	English: Specimen of <i>Brachyglottis huntii</i> (CHR 602367) from the Allan herbarium, Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research ↗
Date	4 October 2016 ↗
Source	Global Biodiversity Information Facility ↗
Author	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research, Allan Herbarium ↗

Licensing [\[edit \]](#)

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Attribution: [Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research, Allan Herbarium / Cc-by-4.0](#)

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- **attribution** – You must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.

Example of File information page for a [specimen image uploaded into Wikimedia Commons](#). The information shown in this page is created using the `{{Information}}` template and is generated by the template pulling data from the structured data added to the image file. Allan Herbarium, Manaaki Whenua - Landcare research. [CC BY 4.0](#)

The uploader should ensure the OpenRefine project is populated with all the necessary information needed to both upload the image file and to create its associated File information page in Wikimedia Commons .

OpenRefine columns to generate an appropriate File information page

file path	filename	caption	Wikitext	date_created	creator_institution	source	rights_type
/Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Calobius littoralis_d_HT.jpg	Holotype of Calobius littoralis (NZAC04041380).jpg <small>new</small> Choose new match	Holotype specimen of Calobius littoralis (NZAC04041380) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>	2014	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294288858	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <small>Choose new match</small>
/Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Cerius tiregius_d_HT.jpg	Holotype of Cerius tiregius (NZAC04041550).jpg <small>new</small> Choose new match	Holotype specimen of Cerius tiregius (NZAC04041550) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>	2014	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294288409	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <small>Choose new match</small>
/Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Cerius otagensis_d_HT.jpg	Holotype of Cerius otagensis (NZAC04041466).jpg <small>new</small> Choose new match	Holotype specimen of Cerius otagensis (NZAC04041466) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>	2014	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4928487346	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <small>Choose new match</small>

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the columns needed to be populated for the {{Information}} template. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The following columns will need to be populated with data to create a File information page via the {{Information}} template - File path, File name, Description/caption, Wikitext containing at least one category, Date of creation of file, Creator of file, Source of file and Copyright licence.

File path

As detailed previously in this documentation, the uploader can use either the Files OpenRefine extension or the Wikimedia Commons tool Pattypan to create the appropriate file path for each image.

File name

This column contains the file name the image file will be known by on Wikimedia Commons. The file name should include the file extension. In the example above the file extension is “.jpg” but other file types are also accepted by Wikimedia Commons. See https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:File_types for further information.

If the file name column has been generated via Pattypan it may be that the file extension is missing. The uploader should ensure that the extension is added to the cells in the file name column.

3 rows										Extens
All	path	File name	description	file extension	date	source	author	permission	license	categories
1.	/Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	Carex comans (CHR 691423)		.png			Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0	{{Cc-by-4.0}}	
2.	/Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sindairii (CHR 695901).png	Carex sindairii (CHR 695901)		.png			Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0	{{Cc-by-4.0}}	
3.	/Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095)		.png			Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0	{{Cc-by-4.0}}	

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the file names lacking a file extension and a new column containing the file extensions. These two columns can be joined to form an appropriate file name column. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This can be done by creating a new column and ensuring all the cells in that column contain the appropriate file extension. The file name column and the file extension column can then be joined to create the appropriate file name.

The screenshot shows the OpenRefine interface with a table containing 3 rows. The columns are: All, path, File name, description, date, source, author, and permis. The 'File name' column is selected, and a context menu is open over it. The menu options are: Facet, Text filter, Edit cells, Edit column, Transpose, Sort..., View, and Reconcile. The 'Reconcile' option is expanded, showing a sub-menu with the following options: Start reconciling... (highlighted), Face Reconcile text in this column with items in another data source, Actions, Copy reconciliation data..., Use values as identifiers..., Add column with URLs of matched entities..., and Add entity identifiers column...

All	path	File name	description	date	source	author	permis
★	1. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png					Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0
★	2. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png					Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0
★	3. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png					Allan Herbarium	CC BY 4.0

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing OpenRefine being instructed to start reconciling the file name column. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once the file name column is created, this column should then be reconciled against Wikimedia Commons. This can be done by clicking the dropdown menu on the file name column, selecting “Reconcile”, and then “Start reconciling...”. Obviously, because these files have yet to be added to Wikimedia Commons, there should be no files in Wikimedia Commons to reconcile against and OpenRefine will return the option of creating a new file. This step is needed to instruct OpenRefine to create new files i.e. upload the images into Wikimedia Commons.

Reconcile column name

Select a service to reconcile against:

<input checked="" type="radio"/> Wikimedia Commons (en) https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/> Wikidata reconcil.link (en) https://wikidata.reconcil.link/en/api	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/> ORCID https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid	<input type="button" value="✕"/>
<input type="radio"/> Bionomia https://api.bionomia.net/reconcile	<input type="button" value="✕"/>

Add standard service...

Discover services...

Next »

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the selection of Wikimedia Commons reconciliation service to Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once the uploader has instructed OpenRefine to reconcile the file name column, they will need to select Wikimedia Commons as the reconciliation service for OpenRefine to reconcile against.

Reconcile column name

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

Sorry, we can't suggest any type for your data.
Please specify a type yourself below.

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
path	<input type="text"/>
wikitext	<input type="text"/>
description	<input type="text"/>
date	<input type="text"/>
source	<input type="text"/>
author	<input type="text"/>
Creative commons license	<input type="text"/>
license	<input type="text"/>
categories	<input type="text"/>
NZAC id	<input type="text"/>

Reconcile against type:

Reconcile against no particular type

Auto-match candidates with high confidence

Maximum number of candidates to return

Back

Start reconciling...

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing reconcile against no particular type. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

When reconciling against Wikimedia Commons, OpenRefine will normally not be able to suggest any type of data to reconcile against. So the uploader should select “Reconcile against no particular type” and then press “Start reconciling...” at the bottom right.

3 rows			
Show as: rows records		Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows	
All	path	File name	description
	1. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	Carex comans (CHR 691423).png <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	
	2. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png	Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	
	3. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create new item Search for match	

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the File name column having been reconciled against Wikimedia Commons . Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Because these files have yet to be added to Wikimedia Commons, the Wikimedia Commons reconciliation service will be unable to find the files. OpenRefine will therefore provide the option to "Create new item" for each image file.

name	description	date	source
C04217627).png	specimen of "Distocupes varians" held at the New Zealand Arthropod Collection	2024-10-01	https://w
38492).png	specimen of "Gelis tenellus" held at the New Zealand Arthropod Collection	2021-07-22	https://w
Toxotrypana australis (N...		2021-07-22	https://w

- Facet
- Text filter
- Edit cells
- Edit column
- Transpose
- Sort...
- View
- Reconcile
 - Start reconciling...
 - Facets
 - Actions
 - Match each cell to its best candidate
 - Create a new item for each cell...**
 - Create one new item for similar cells
 - Mark to create one new item for each cell in this column for all current filtered rows
 - Match all filtered cells
 - Discard reconciliation judgments
 - Clear reconciliation data
 - Copy reconciliation data...
 - Use values as identifiers...
 - Add column with URLs of matched entities...
 - Add entity identifiers column...

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the selection of the create new item option. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To ensure OpenRefine is instructed to “create new file” for all the image files, select the dropdown menu in the file name column, select “Reconcile”, then “Actions” and finally “Create a new item for each cell...”.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing column title bright green bar. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The bar below the column title will change colour to bright green and the column will show that new files will be created in Wikimedia Commons based on these file names.

Description/caption

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a recommended caption for a file. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

A caption or description for each file also needs to be created. This should be a brief but complete statement about the content displayed by each image file. It is recommended that the name of the species, the institution that holds that specimen as well as the institution catalogue number be used to create a caption or description for the file. That is: “Specimen of [current name of the species] held at [name of holding institution] (“Institutional catalogue code”). If the specimen is a type specimen this should also be indicated in the caption.

Date of inception

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the date of creation/inception for a file. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The date of the creation of the image file should be added as a structured data statement. This statement uses the Wikidata "[inception](#)" (P571) property.

Creator

The creator of the image file should be added to the OpenRefine project as part of a reconciled against Wikidata column. For natural history specimens the creator will normally be the institution that undertook the digitization and created the image file being uploaded to Wikimedia Commons. The institution that digitised the specimen should have an existing Wikidata item that the OpenRefine column can be reconciled against. If no Wikidata item exists for that institution one should be created.

Where an individual working for the institution has been credited with creating that file, they too can be added as a creator. A separate column listing that individual should be created in OpenRefine and the name string for that individual should be added and reconciled against Wikidata, matching to the existing or newly created Wikidata item for that individual.

Note where the OpenRefine project has been generated via a spreadsheet created via Patten the creator column will normally be titled "author". The uploader has the option of changing the column name if needed.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the reconciliation of a column containing the creator of the image files. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To reconcile the creator column against Wikidata first select the dropdown menu for that column and choose “Reconcile” and then “Start reconciling ...”.

Reconcile column author

Select a service to reconcile against:

Wikimedia Commons (en)
<https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api>

Wikidata reconcil.link (en)
<https://wikidata.reconci.link/en/api>

ORCID
<https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid>

Bionomia
<https://api.bionomia.net/reconcile>

Add standard service...

Discover services...

Next »

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the selection of the Wikidata reconciliation service. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The reconciliation service will then be chosen. In this case reconciliation against the Wikidata reconciliation service is appropriate.

Reconcile column author

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

- human
Q5
- herbarium
Q181916
- entity
Q35120

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
path	<input type="text"/>
File name	<input type="text"/>
description	<input type="text"/>
Wikitext	<input type="text"/>
date	<input type="text"/>
source	<input type="text"/>
permission	<input type="text"/>
license	<input type="text"/>
categories	<input type="text"/>
categories 1	<input type="text"/>
blank column	<input type="text"/>

Reconcile against type:
 Reconcile against no particular type
 Auto-match candidates with high confidence
 Maximum number of candidates to return

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the type entity against which the author/creator column is being reconciled. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Pick the type of entity to reconcile against. In the above example, as the creator of the file is the Allan Herbarium, the type of entity that name string should be reconciled against is “herbarium”. Then press “Start reconciling”.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a successfully reconciled cell. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The cells in that column should successfully reconcile and to indicate this the bar under the title of the column should turn green. If there are any unreconciled cells the bar will only be partially green and work will have to be undertaken to ensure all name strings are successfully reconciled.

Source

The source of the file should also be added to the OpenRefine project.

Image files having an online presence with an appropriate copyright license

If the files to be uploaded to Wikimedia Commons already have an online presence, the URL for the related web page should be included as the source of the file. This URL will serve as proof that the files have an appropriate copyright licence which gives permission for those files to be reused in Wikimedia Commons.

Image files have no online presence or no appropriate copyright license

If the files proposed to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons **DO NOT** have a digital source that also shows an acceptable to Wikimedia Commons copyright reuse licence, it is recommended that the uploader follows the Volunteer Response Team (VRT) process https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Volunteer_Response_Team.

The VRT process should be commenced **prior** to upload. Once started, the image files are then able to be uploaded with the template `{{Permission pending}}` on each File information page in addition to the copyright license chosen by the copyright holding institution.

Once the VRT volunteer is satisfied that the permission statement provided via the process is sufficient, they will replace the permission pending template with the `{{PermissionTicket}}` template.

Further guidance on this process to employees of the copyright holder of the image can be found in *Wikimedia Commons uploads : Uploading of images by an employee of the copyright holder* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556>.

Copyright licence

If the file is copyrighted, the following Wikimedia Commons official policy sets out acceptable licenses and other information for image file uploads <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Licensing>.

The copyright license empowering the reuse of the image should be added to the image file as a structured data statement. A column should be added to the OpenRefine project providing the appropriate reuse licence attached to each of the image files being uploaded and this should be reconciled against Wikidata.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the reconciliation of the copyright licence column. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To reconcile those cells against Wikidata by first selecting “Reconcile” from the license column dropdown menu and then select “Start reconciling ...”

Reconcile column license

Select a service to reconcile against:

<input type="radio"/>	Wikimedia Commons (en) https://commonsreconcile.toolforge.org/en/api	<input type="button" value="x"/>
<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Wikidata reconci.link (en) https://wikidata.reconci.link/en/api	<input type="button" value="x"/>
<input type="radio"/>	ORCID https://refine.codefork.com/reconcile/orcid	<input type="button" value="x"/>
<input type="radio"/>	Bionomia https://api.bionomia.net/reconcile	<input type="button" value="x"/>

Add standard service...

Discover services...

Next »

Cancel

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Choose the reconciliation service, again the Wikidata reconciliation service is appropriate. Then press “Next”.

Reconcile column license

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

- Creative Commons license
Q284742
- free license
Q196294
- open license
Q30939938
- proprietary license
Q3238057
- entity
Q35120

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
path	<input type="text"/>
File name	<input type="text"/>
description	<input type="text"/>
Wikitext	<input type="text"/>
date	<input type="text"/>
source	<input type="text"/>
author	<input type="text"/>
permission	<input type="text"/>
categories	<input type="text"/>
categories 1	<input type="text"/>
blank column	<input type="text"/>

- Reconcile against type:
 - Reconcile against no particular type
 - Auto-match candidates with high confidence
- Maximum number of candidates to return

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Choose the type of entity to reconcile the column data against. In this case the appropriate entity is the Creative Commons licence. The press “Start reconciling ... “

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a successfully reconciled cell. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Wikimedia Commons category

Each uploaded image file should be able to be placed in at least one Wikimedia Commons category. For natural history specimen uploads it is recommended that the category be either the institution category for the institution supplying the image or the species category for the specimen depicted in the image file or ideally both. For more information on Wikimedia Commons categories see

<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Categories>.

The more Wikimedia Commons categories appropriately added to the image file the higher the likelihood of others finding the image file for reuse.

In OpenRefine the Wikimedia Commons category for the image file can be added either through a written Wikitext column or via GREL expressions that generates the appropriate Wikitext for the image file.

Wikitext

Wikitext is the markup language used by Wikimedia Commons to format the required media file page. Each image file needs Wikitext to ensure the file page is appropriately created for the image and provides the minimum information about that image. Wikitext cheatsheet can be found here <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Help:Cheatsheet>

There are several methods to generate the required Wikitext. Examples include adding basic written Wikitext to the appropriate OpenRefine column. Alternatively the Wikitext for the file can be generated via a GREL expression.

Written Wikitext

```
=={{int:filedesc}}==
{{Information}}

=={{int:license-header}}==
{{License from structured data}}
```

```
[[Category:New Zealand Arthropod Collection]]
```

The above written Wikitext uses the example of a New Zealand Arthropod specimen image where the required information for that image file is generated via the `{{Information}}` template. As explained previously, unlike many Wikimedia Commons templates, the `{{Information}}` template can extract the necessary information from structured data added to the image file. The Wikitext will also show an appropriate reuse licence generated from the licence added to the structured data of the image and should also give a category, in this example the New Zealand Arthropod Collection, for the institution providing the image.

So long as the OpenRefine project contains all the necessary data that will be added to the image files, written Wikitext similar to the above example can be used to generate the Information page of the image file on Wikimedia Commons.

Example file

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_\(CHR_602367\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Brachyglottis_huntii_(CHR_602367).jpg)

Example OpenRefine project with Wikitext generated by written text

All	path	wikitext	name
☆	1. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/NZAC sample upload/NZAC04217627.png	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>	Distocupes varians (NZAC04217627).png
☆	2. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/NZAC sample upload/NZAC04238492.png	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>	Gelis tenellus (NZAC04238492).png
☆	3. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/NZAC sample upload/NZAC04193008.png	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>	Toxotrypana australis (NZAC04193008).png edit

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

description	date	source	author	Creative commons license
specimen of "Distocupes varians" held at the New Zealand Arthropod Collection	2024-10-01	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3419940302	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match
specimen of "Gelis tenellus" held at the New Zealand Arthropod Collection	2021-07-22	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/3329752304	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match	edit Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match
specimen of "Toxotrypana australis" held at the New Zealand Arthropod Collection	2021-07-22	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/2273872533	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This Wikitext can be added to the cells in a column in an OpenRefine project and be applied to multiple image files. However one limitation of the above Wikitext is that the Wikimedia Commons category would have to apply to all the file images being uploaded.

Wikitext generated via GREL expression

```
"=={{int:filedesc}}==\n" +
"{{Information}}\n\n" +
```

```
"=={{int:license-header}}==\n" +
"{{License from structured data}}\n\n" +
if(isNull(value), "", value) +
if(or(isError(cells["categories"].value), isBlank(cells["categories"].value)), "", "\n[" +
cells["categories"].value.trim() + "]]") +
if(or(isError(cells["categories 1"].value), isBlank(cells["categories 1"].value)), "", "\n[" +
cells["categories 1"].value.trim() + "]]")
```

The above GREL expression will generate the Wikitext to be added to image files. The Wikitext will create the File information page on Wikimedia Commons using both the Wikimedia Commons {{Information}} template along with the Wikimedia Commons {{Licence from structured data}} template. Each of these templates will pull from the structured data added to the image file.

The categories portion of the GREL expression will pull data from each cell in the appropriately titled OpenRefine project category column. The category column title should **exactly** match the title given in the GREL expression. If these do not match the expression will fail to generate the needed Wikitext in the OpenRefine project.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

To generate the appropriate Wikitext in OpenRefine via this GREL expression select the Wikitext column dropdown menu, then select “Edit cells” and choose “Transform”. Then add the General Refine Expression Language (GREL) code.

Custom text transform on column Wikitext

Expression Language General Refine Expression Language (GREL) ▾

```

"=={{int:filedesc}}==\n" +
"{{Information}}\n\n" +

"=={{int:license-header}}==\n" +
"{{License from structured data}}\n\n" +
if(isNull(value), "", value) +
if(or(isError(cells["categories"].value),
isBlank(cells["categories"].value)), "", "\n[" +
cells["categories"].value.trim() + "])" +
if(or(isError(cells["categories 1"].value),
isBlank(cells["categories 1"].value)), "", "\n[" +
cells["categories 1"].value.trim() + "])"

```

No syntax error.

Preview History Starred Help

row	value	"=={{int:filedesc}}==\n" + "{{ ...
1.	null	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex comans (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>
2.	null	=={{int:filedesc}}==

On error keep original Re-transform up to times until no change
 set to blank
 store error

OK **Cancel**

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the GREL code added to the Wikitext column and the preview of the generated Wikitext. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

If the GREL is correctly formatted it will produce the needed Wikitext in the Preview tab. Press "OK" to insert the Wikitext generated by GREL in the appropriate cells in the Wikitext column.

Wikitext
<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex comans (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>
<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex sinclairii]] </pre>
<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex dipsacea (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a Wikitext column generated via a GREL expression. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Example file:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Carex_comans_\(CHR_691423\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Carex_comans_(CHR_691423).png)

Example OpenRefine project with GREL expression generating Wikitext

3 rows						Exten
Show as: rows records						Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows
						« first < previous 1 - 3
All	path	File name	description	Wikitext	date	
	1. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	Carex comans (CHR 691423).png <small>new</small> Choose new match	specimen of Carex comans held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 691423)	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex comans (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>	2025-05-27	
	2. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png	Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png <small>new</small> Choose new match	specimen of Carex sinclairii held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 695901)	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex sinclairii]] </pre>	2025-05-27	
	3. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png <small>new</small> Choose new match	specimen of Carex dipsacea held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 688095)	<pre> =={{int:filedesc}}== {{Information}} =={{int:license-header}}== {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex dipsacea (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>	2025-05-28	

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

source	author	license	categories	categories 1	blank column
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4903556376	Allan Herbarium Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match	Category:Allan Herbarium	Category:Carex comans (herbarium specimens)	
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4981886358	Allan Herbarium Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match	Category:Allan Herbarium	Category:Carex sinclairii	
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4903564116	Allan Herbarium Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match	Category:Allan Herbarium	Category:Carex dipsacea (herbarium specimens)	

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

For more information on OpenRefine expressions see the OpenRefine documentation <https://openrefine.org/docs/manual/expressions>. Frequently used GREL functions can be explored here <https://github.com/OpenRefine/OpenRefine/wiki/Recipe>.

Structured Data on Commons statements

As explained previously, it is highly recommended that *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400> be followed to ensure appropriate additional structured data statements are added to specimen image files uploaded to Wikimedia Commons. Not only will the addition of this structured data improve usability and findability of these image files, it may also be used in the future to generate a Wikimedia Commons Information file page via the Wikimedia Commons `{{Specimen}}` template.

The guidance for the additional structured data statements recommended to be added to a natural history specimen file image will depend on what sort of specimen the image file depicts. The guidance will differ if the image file depicts a type specimen that has an existing related Wikidata item or whether the image file depicts an “ordinary” specimen.

Type specimen images

Where the OpenRefine project covers the upload of **type specimen** images, the following supplementary columns should also be created in that OpenRefine project.

Depicts

Where the image is a type specimen the following depicts statements may be added. A separate OpenRefine column should be created for each needed depicts statement to be added to a specimen image file. More information on the motivation for recommending these multiple “depicts” statements can be found in the data model documentation *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400>.

Depicts (P180)	Wikidata item for the taxonomic name of the species given in file metadata or title.
Depicts (P180)	Wikidata item for the currently accepted valid taxonomic name of species.
Depicts (P180)	Wikidata item for that type specimen.
Depicts (P180)	holotype (Q1061403), syntype (Q719822), paratype (Q926578) lectotype (Q2439719), paralectotype (Q19353473), neotype (Q3874702), allotype (Q19353437).

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> depicts taxon name	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> current name	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> depicts holotype Wikidata item	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> depicts holotype
Anthribus tessellatus	Opanthribus tessellatus	holotype of Anthribus tessellatus	holotype
Calibius littoralis		holotype of Calibius littoralis	holotype
			holotype
Cerius otagensis		holotype of Cerius otagensis	holotype

Screenshot of an OpenRefine Project showing four columns that, once reconciled against Wikidata, will provide the recommended “depicts” statements. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Each column containing “depicts” data will need to be reconciled against Wikidata.

Reconcile column current_accepted_name

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

- taxon
Q16521
- cultivar
Q4886
- entity
Q35120

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
path	<input type="text"/>
filename	<input type="text"/>
caption	<input type="text"/>
Wikitext	<input type="text"/>
rights_status	<input type="text"/>
rights_type	<input type="text"/>
date_created	<input type="text"/>
holding_institution	<input type="text"/>
collection_institution	<input type="text"/>
media_type	<input type="text"/>
creator	<input type="text"/>
sponsor	<input type="text"/>

Reconcile against type:

Reconcile against no particular type

Auto-match candidates with high confidence

Maximum number of candidates to return

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the entity the current accepted name column is being reconciled against. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

When reconciling columns against Wikidata the appropriate entity type to be reconciled against needs to be chosen. For example in the above screenshot the entity type for an OpenRefine column providing data on the currently accepted species name will be “taxon”.

One of the recommended “depicts” statements will link the image file of the type specimen to the **Wikidata item** for that type specimen. As a result of this linking, it is unnecessary to duplicate the data held in that Wikidata item in the structured data for that type specimen image file.

Copyright status

This structured data statement explains whether the image file is copyrighted, is copyrighted and the copyright holder has dedicated the image file to the public domain, or the image has ascended to the public domain.

A screenshot of a dropdown menu titled 'copyright status'. The menu is open, showing two options: 'public domain' and 'copyrighted'. The 'copyrighted' option is currently selected and highlighted in white, while 'public domain' is in a light grey background.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The above image shows two examples of copyright status statements.

Reconcile column copyright status

Reconcile each cell to an entity of one of these types:

- copyright status of set
Q73568642
- copyright status
Q50424085
- legal term or legal concept
Q2135465
- exclusive right
Q1146011
- entity
Q35120

Reconcile against type:

Reconcile against no particular type

Auto-match candidates with high confidence

Maximum number of candidates to return

Also use relevant details from other columns:

Column	As property
path	<input type="text"/>
File name	<input type="text"/>
description	<input type="text"/>
Wikitext	<input type="text"/>
date	<input type="text"/>
source	<input type="text"/>
author	<input type="text"/>
license	<input type="text"/>
categories	<input type="text"/>
categories 1	<input type="text"/>
blank column	<input type="text"/>
depicts	<input type="text"/>

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

When reconciling against Wikidata the type of entity the copyright status column should be reconciled against is “copyright status”.

Copyright licence

It is important to ensure a structured data statement is added giving the copyright licence the image is released under. This is especially important if the `{{License from structured data}}` template is used in the Wikitext for the image file to generate information on the legal ability to reuse the file. The reconciled cells should already exist in the OpenRefine project if the uploader has followed the advice given in the above “File information data” section of this document.

Collection

This structured data statement links to the natural history collection and the natural history institution that holds both the specimen image file and the specimen depicted in their collection. It is recommended that two structured data statements about the collections be made to link both the natural history collection as well as the institution that oversees that collection. For example the Allan Herbarium and the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute.

▼ collection	▼ institution
Allan Herbarium	New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute
Allan Herbarium	New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute
Allan Herbarium	New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute
Allan Herbarium	New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

In the above example the collection where the image file and specimen are held is the Allan Herbarium and the managing institution is the New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science. Both should be added as the “collection” via structured data statements on the image file.

Instance of

A column should be created in the OpenRefine project giving data stating that the image file is a photograph. This column should also be reconciled against Wikidata. When reconciling, care should be taken to ensure this “instance of” column is successfully reconciled against the correct Wikidata item, for example photograph [Q125191](#)

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

If OpenRefine fails to provide the appropriate match the uploader may be required to press the “Search for match” on the bottom right under the list of reconciliation options.

Search for match

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The correct item for the concept of photograph should then be selected. If the item for a photograph i.e. [Q125191](#) fails to appear in the list offered, this QID can be substituted in the search box to ensure the correct Wikidata item is selected for reconciliation.

Sponsor

A Wikidata reconciled OpenRefine column should be created stating the digitisation sponsor of the image files, if this is known. The digitisation sponsor can be an institution or an individual.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a column with digitisation sponsor data that has been reconciled against Wikidata. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Copyright holder

Where different from the institution or individual listed in the creator column, an OpenRefine column should be created stating the institution or individual that holds the copyright of the image. This column should again be reconciled against Wikidata.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a column that has been reconciled against Wikidata for the copyright holder of the image files. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Example OpenRefine project for type specimen image upload

The below screenshots show an example OpenRefine project giving column headings and a layout that follows the Crosswalk documentation for the Natural History Specimen Data model outlined here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881782>.

3 matching records (6 total)					Schema *	Issues 1	Preview	Extension
Show as: rows records		Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 records			« first < previous 1 - 5 next »			
All	file path	filename	caption	Wikitext				
1.	/Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Calobius littoralis_d_HT.jpg	Holotype of Calobius littoralis (NZAC04041380).jpg Choose new match	Holotype specimen of Calobius littoralis (NZAC04041380) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection	<pre> {{int:filedesc}}= {{Information}} {{int:license-header}}= {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>				
3.	/Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Cerius triregius_d_HT.jpg	Holotype of Cerius triregius (NZAC04041550).jpg Choose new match	Holotype specimen of Cerius triregius (NZAC04041550) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection	<pre> {{int:filedesc}}= {{Information}} {{int:license-header}}= {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>				
5.	/Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Cerius otagensis_d_HT.jpg	Holotype of Cerius otagensis (NZAC04041466).jpg Choose new match	Holotype specimen of Cerius otagensis (NZAC04041466) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection	<pre> {{int:filedesc}}= {{Information}} {{int:license-header}}= {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]] </pre>				

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

3 matching records (6 total)									Schema *	Issues 1	Preview	Extensions	Wikib
Show as: rows records		Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 records							« first < previous 1 - 5 next »				
current_accepted_name	type_status	type_specimen	rights_status	rights_type	date_created	institution	institution_collection	media_type					
Calobius littoralis Choose new match	holotype Choose new match	holotype of Calobius littoralis Choose new match	copyrighted Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match	2014	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science Choose new match	New Zealand Arthropod Collection Choose new match	photograph Choose new match					
Cerius triregius Choose new match	holotype Choose new match	holotype of Cerius triregius Choose new match	copyrighted Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match	2014	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science Choose new match	New Zealand Arthropod Collection Choose new match	photograph Choose new match					
Cerius otagensis Choose new match	holotype Choose new match	holotype of Cerius otagensis Choose new match	copyrighted Choose new match	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Choose new match	2014	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science Choose new match	New Zealand Arthropod Collection Choose new match	photograph Choose new match					

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

review					Extensions	Wikibase ▾				
500 1000 records					« first	« previous	1	- 5	next »	last »
creator_institution	creator_individual	sponsor	rights_holder	source						
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	Birgit E. Rhode <small>Choose new match</small>	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294288858						
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	Birgit E. Rhode <small>Choose new match</small>	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294288409						
Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	Birgit E. Rhode <small>Choose new match</small>	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>	https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4928487346						

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Example OpenRefine schema for type specimen image upload

The below images give an example OpenRefine schema guiding the upload of type specimen image files and their associated structured data into Wikimedia Commons.

3 matching records (6 total) Schema * Issues 6 Preview

Target Wikibase instance: Wikimedia Commons ▾

Start from an existing schema: Select... Save schema

file path filename caption Wikitext current_accepted_name type_status type_specimen rights_status rights_type date_created institution institu

filename remove

File path: file path

File name: filename

Wikitext: Wikitext override existing wikitext

Captions

en caption override if present remove

+ add caption

Statements

depicts

current_accepted_na... remove

configure

+ add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference

type_stat... remove

configure

+ add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference

type_specim... remove

configure

+ add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference

+ add value

copyright status

rights_stat... remove

configure

+ add qualifier

▶ 1 references

+ add reference

+ add value

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

copyright license	rights_ty...	remove configure + add qualifier + add reference + add value
inception	date_creat...	remove configure + add qualifier + add reference + add value
collection	institution	remove configure remove + add qualifier + add reference
	institution_collect...	remove configure remove + add qualifier + add reference + add value
instance of	media_ty...	remove configure + add qualifier + add reference + add value

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

creator	creator_institut...	remove configure + add qualifier + add reference
	creator_individ...	remove configure + add qualifier + add reference + add value
sponsor	sponsor	remove configure remove + add qualifier + add reference + add value
copyright holder	rights_hol...	remove configure + add qualifier
	reference URL	remove remove remove + add + add reference + add value
source of file	file available on the internet	remove configure remove remove + add qualifier

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Example type specimen image

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Odontria_cassinae_Given,_1952_NZAC04067248.jpg

“Ordinary” specimen images

Where the image file depicts an “ordinary” specimen i.e. a specimen that is NOT a type specimen, the following additional structured data statements are needed. Where the structured data statements added are related to the natural history specimen depicted in the image file, the *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400> recommends the addition of a qualifier statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557). This qualifier highlights that such structured data statements relate to the specimen depicted rather than the media file itself.

Depicts

Where the image is an “ordinary” specimen, the depicts statements should be added in a similar manner to a type specimen image file. That is, separate OpenRefine columns should be created for each required depicts statement and the “depicts” values should be reconciled against Wikidata. It may be that the taxonomic name is not in Wikidata in which case it is recommended that a new Wikidata item be created for that taxonomic name.

Depicts (P180)	Wikidata item for the taxonomic name of the species given in file metadata or title.
Depicts (P180)	Wikidata item for the currently accepted valid taxonomic name of species

Inventory number

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing a specimen inventory number. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

An OpenRefine column should be created containing a text string of the institution inventory number for each specimen depicted by each image. When uploading this data into Wikimedia Commons the uploader should ensure this data statement includes the addition of a qualifier statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557)

Date of collection of specimen

A screenshot of an OpenRefine column header labeled 'collection_date' with a dropdown arrow. Below the header, the date '2024-01-31' is displayed in a light gray box.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

An OpenRefine column should be created containing the date of collection of the specimen depicted by each image. When uploading this data into Wikimedia Commons the uploader should ensure this data statement includes the addition of a qualifier statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557)

Collector of physical specimen

A screenshot of two OpenRefine columns. The first column, 'collector', shows 'Brian D. Rance' with a 'Choose new match' link. The second column, 'collector_2', shows 'Geoff Rogers' with a 'Choose new match' link. Below these, there are two more rows: 'Colin Ogle' and 'Lyneke Onderwater', each with a 'Choose new match' link.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing two collector columns. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

One or more OpenRefine columns should be created for the collectors of the specimen depicted by each image. These columns should then be carefully reconciled against Wikidata. This disambiguation of collectors can be time consuming. If Wikidata items do not exist for the collectors of the specimen depicted it is recommended that items be created for them. When uploading this data into Wikimedia Commons the uploader should ensure this data statement includes the addition of a qualifier statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557)

Specimen classifier

An OpenRefine column should be created for the specimen classifier. This column should carefully be reconciled against Wikidata. Again this disambiguation of people, that is matching the name strings to appropriate Wikidata items representing those people, may be time consuming. If Wikidata items do not exist for the classifier or determiner of the specimen depicted it is recommended that Wikidata items be created for them. When uploading this data into Wikimedia Commons the uploader should ensure this data statement includes the addition of a qualifier statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557)

Location collected

▼ location_collected	▼ verbatim_collection_location
Mavora Lakes Conservation Park Choose new match	True left of Mararoa River, between Boundary Hut and Taipo Hut section of Upper Mararoa Valley

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

An OpenRefine column should be created for the collection location of the specimen depicted by image. Again this column should be reconciled against Wikidata. Like people names, reconciling the location name string to the appropriate Wikidata item for that location can be time consuming. The uploader should also ensure that a column be created containing the verbatim collection location as given in the data related to the depicted specimen.

It may be that there is no Wikidata item that is an exact match to the collection location. If this is the case, the uploader should reconcile the collection location name string against the Wikidata item that is most applicable for that name string. See for example the above screenshot where the verbatim collection location “True left of Mararoa River, between Boundary Hut and Taipo Hut section of Upper Mararoa Valley” has been reconciled to the Wikidata item for [Mavora Lakes Conservation Park](#) (Q86665819), a locality that contains the collection location of the specimen depicted by the file image.

The uploader should also ensure that when uploading this data into Wikimedia Commons this data statement includes a qualifier statement [object named as](#) (P1932) linking to the name string for the collection location. Another qualifier should also be added stating that the location collector statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557).

Coordinates for location collected

▼ coordinate_location
-45.10891, 168.225347

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the coordinate location format in an OpenRefine project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Where possible the coordinates for the location the specimen depicted by the image file should be included as a structured data statement on that image file. A text string for the latitude and longitude coordinates separated by a comma should be provided in an OpenRefine column. When uploading this structured data statement into Wikimedia Commons the editor should include a qualifying statement stating that [object of statement has role](#) (P3831) → [location collected](#) (Q138018332). Another qualifier should also be added stating that the coordinate location statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557).

Sex of depicted specimen

If this data is provided in the originating dataset, an OpenRefine column should be created to give the sex of the specimen depicted by the image. This column again should be reconciled against Wikidata. Again a qualifier should be added stating that the sex of the specimen statement [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557).

Significant event

Where the specimen depicted is associated with a significant event, for example the specimen was collected during a research expedition, an OpenRefine column can be created and the significant event statement should be added to the image file. This column should be reconciled against Wikidata matching the significant event to the Wikidata item for that event. If no Wikidata item exists for that significant event it is recommended a Wikidata item be created for it. A qualifier should be added to the significant event statement stating that it [applies to part](#) (P518) → [physical object](#) (Q223557).

Example OpenRefine project for “ordinary” specimen image upload

This example uses the documentation *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400> to guide the creation of the OpenRefine project.

	path	filename	caption	Wikitext	current_accepted_name
1.	./Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	specimen of Carex comans held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 691423)	<pre> {{#if:filedesc}} {{Information}} {{#if:license-header}} {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex comans (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>	Carex comans
2.	./Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png	Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png	specimen of Carex sinclairii held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 695901)	<pre> {{#if:filedesc}} {{Information}} {{#if:license-header}} {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex sinclairii]] </pre>	Carex sinclairii
3.	./Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	specimen of Carex dipsacea held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 688095)	<pre> {{#if:filedesc}} {{Information}} {{#if:license-header}} {{License from structured data}} [[Category:Allan Herbarium]] [[Category:Carex dipsacea (herbarium specimens)]] </pre>	Carex dipsacea

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

3 rows Extensions Wikibas

Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows « first < previous 1 - 3 next > last

rights_status	rights_type	date_created	holding_institution	collection_institution	media_type	creator	sponsor	rights_holder
copyrighted <small>Choose new match</small>	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <small>Choose new match</small>	2025-05-27	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>	Allan Herbarium <small>Choose new match</small>	photograph <small>Choose new match</small>	Allan Herbarium <small>Choose new match</small>	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>
copyrighted <small>Choose new match</small>	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <small>Choose new match</small>	2025-05-27	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>	Allan Herbarium <small>Choose new match</small>	photograph <small>Choose new match</small>	Allan Herbarium <small>Choose new match</small>	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>
copyrighted <small>Choose new match</small>	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <small>Choose new match</small>	2025-05-28	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>	Allan Herbarium <small>Choose new match</small>	photograph <small>Choose new match</small>	Allan Herbarium <small>Choose new match</small>	Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research <small>Choose new match</small>	New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science <small>Choose new match</small>

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

source	inventory_number	collection_date	collector	collector_2	classifier	classifier_2	location_collected	verbatim_collection_location	coordinate_location
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4903556376	CHR 691423	2024-01-31	Brian D. Rance <small>Choose new match</small>	Geoff Rogers <small>Choose new match</small>	Brian D. Rance <small>Choose new match</small>		Mavora Lakes Conservation Park <small>Choose new match</small>	True left of Mararoa River, between Boundary Hut and Taipo Hut section of Upper Mararoa Valley	-45.10891, 168.225347
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/4981886358	CHR 695901	2024-01-07	Colin Ogle <small>Choose new match</small>	Lyneke Onderwater <small>Choose new match</small>	Colin Ogle <small>Choose new match</small>		Whanganui <small>Choose new match</small>	Whanganui, Virginia Road, Quaker Settlement	-39.906355, 175.028375
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/49035564116	CHR 688095	2024-01-24	Alice Shanks <small>Choose new match</small>	Lynn Galloway <small>Choose new match</small>	Alice Shanks <small>Choose new match</small>	Lynn Galloway <small>Choose new match</small>	Galloway Wetlands <small>Choose new match</small>	Galloway Wetland QE II, Blinkbonnie Farm, Ashburton Forks	-43.72019, 171.580144

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Example OpenRefine schema for “ordinary” specimen image upload

The below images give an example OpenRefine schema guiding the upload of both “ordinary” specimen image files and their associated structured data into Wikimedia Commons.

3 rows Schema * Issues 3 Preview

Target Wikibase instance: Wikimedia Commons

Start from an existing schema: Select... Save schema

path filename caption Wikitext current_accepted_name rights_status rights_type date_created holding_institution collection_institution media_type cre
 collector_2 classifier classifier_2 blank column

filename remove

File path: path remove

File name: filename remove

Wikitext: Wikitext remove override existing wikitext

Captions

en caption remove override if present add caption

Statements

depicts remove configure add qualifier paste reference

current_accepted_na... remove

1 references

copy remove

reference URL source remove

retrieved 2026-03-08 remove

+ add add reference add value

copyright status remove configure add qualifier paste reference

rights_stat... remove

1 references add reference add value

copyright license remove configure add qualifier paste reference

rights_ty... remove

1 references add reference add value

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

inception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> date_creat... ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> holding_institut... object of state holding institution ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> collection_institut... object of state holding collection ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure remove + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> media_ty... ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value
creator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> creator ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure + add qualifier paste reference + add reference + add value

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

sponsor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sponsor object of state digitization sponsor ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure remove + add qualifier + add reference + add value
copyright holder	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> rights_hol... ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure + add qualifier + add reference + add value
source of file	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> file available on the internet operator Global Biodiversity described at U source ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure remove remove + add qualifier + add reference + add value
inventory number	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> inventory_num... applies to part physical object ▶ 1 references 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> remove configure remove + add qualifier + add reference

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

collection date	<div> <div>collection_d... </div> <div> <div>applies to part</div> <div>physical object</div> </div> <div>▶ 1 references</div> </div>	<div>remove</div> <div>configure</div> <div>remove</div> <div>+ add qualifier</div> <div>+ add reference</div> <div>+ add value</div>
collector	<div> <div>collector </div> <div> <div>series ordinal</div> <div>1</div> </div> <div> <div>applies to part</div> <div>physical object</div> </div> <div>▶ 1 references</div> </div>	<div>remove</div> <div>configure</div> <div>remove</div> <div>remove</div> <div>+ add qualifier</div> <div>+ add reference</div>
	<div> <div>collector... </div> <div> <div>series ordinal</div> <div>2</div> </div> <div> <div>applies to part</div> <div>physical object</div> </div> <div>▶ 1 references</div> </div>	
specimen classifier	<div> <div>classifier </div> <div> <div>series ordinal</div> <div>1</div> </div> <div> <div>applies to part</div> <div>physical object</div> </div> </div>	<div>remove</div> <div>configure</div> <div>remove</div> <div>remove</div> <div>+ add qualifier</div>

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

location collected	<div> <div>location_collec... </div> <div> <div>object named</div> <div>verbatim_collection_I...</div> </div> <div> <div>applies to part</div> <div>physical object</div> </div> <div>▶ 1 references</div> </div>	<div>remove</div> <div>configure</div> <div>remove</div> <div>remove</div> <div>+ add qualifier</div> <div>+ add reference</div> <div>+ add value</div>
coordinate location	<div> <div>coordinate_locat... </div> <div> <div>object of state</div> <div>location collected</div> </div> <div> <div>applies to part</div> <div>physical object</div> </div> <div>▶ 1 references</div> </div>	<div>remove</div> <div>configure</div> <div>remove</div> <div>remove</div> <div>+ add qualifier</div> <div>+ add reference</div> <div>+ add value</div>

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Example “ordinary” specimen image

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Carex_comans_\(CHR_691423\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Carex_comans_(CHR_691423).png)

Uploading files to Wikimedia Commons

Once both the File information tab requirements are added to the OpenRefine project along with all the required structured data statements, the uploader can begin the process of uploading the image files and their accompanying structured data into Wikimedia Commons.

The uploader should double check whether any OpenRefine columns need to be reconciled against Wikidata before proceeding.

The uploader should also double check that the file name column has been reconciled against Wikimedia Commons and OpenRefine has been instructed to “create new item” for each of those image files. This will ensure the image files and their prepared structured data statements are uploaded into Wikimedia Commons when the data in the OpenRefine project is exported to that platform.

Create OpenRefine schema

Once satisfied that all the necessary data statements are prepared, the uploader then needs to create an OpenRefine schema.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The uploader does this by clicking on the Wikibase tab at the top righthand side of the OpenRefine project, and selecting “Edit Wikibase schema” from the dropdown menu.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project showing the Schema tab and the selection of Wikimedia Commons as the target Wikibase instance. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

This will generate three extra tabs in the OpenRefine project. These can be seen next to the tab containing the rows of data for the project. In the Schema tab the uploader should select the Target Wikibase instance. As the image files are being uploaded into Wikimedia Commons this is the Wikibase instance that should be selected.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The uploader should drag and drop the file name column into the “type file name or drag reconciled column” box as this is the image file name column that OpenRefine has been instructed to upload to Wikimedia Commons. Then add the file path column into the “File path” box. Drag and drop the file name column to the “File name” box and finally the Wikitext column heading to the “Wikitext” box.

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then click the blue “+ add caption” and choose the language code for the language of the caption (in the above example the language chosen is English) and then drag and drop the description/caption column into that “caption” box.

Statements

inception

date

1 references

copy

reference URL	source
retrieved	2026-02-11

remove
configure
+ add qualifier
remove
remove
remove
+ add
+ add reference
+ add value

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Then press the blue “+ add statement” to start adding statements. The uploader should add the necessary statements to the schema as set out in the guiding documentation *Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400>.

The uploader is again reminded that the statements to be added via the OpenRefine schema will depend on whether the specimen depicted by the image file is a type specimen or an “ordinary” specimen.

Statements

inception

date

1 references

copy

reference URL	source
retrieved	2026-02-11

remove
configure
+ add qualifier
paste reference
remove
remove
remove
+ add
+ add reference
+ add value

Statements

source of file

file available on the internet

operator Global Biodiversity

described at U source

1 references

copy

reference URL	source
retrieved	2026-02-11

remove
configure
remove
remove
+ add qualifier
+ add
+ add reference
+ add value

Statements

copyright license

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Interr

1 references

copy

reference URL	source
retrieved	2026-02-11

remove
configure
+ add qualifier
remove
remove
+ add

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Check Issues and Preview

Before commencing the upload editors should check both the issues tab and the Preview tab provided by the OpenRefine project.

Issues tab

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The Issues tab will always contain a “New media upload” warning alerting the uploader they will be uploading new files to Wikimedia Commons.

Preview tab

The preview tab will provide a summary of the edits that will be made to Wikimedia Commons when each image file is uploaded. The editor should double check that edits to be made are as expected.

Below is an example of a preview for a holotype specimen image file about to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons.

3 matching rows (6 total) Schema * Issues 3 Preview

This tab shows the first edits (out of 3) that will be made once you upload the changes to [Wikimedia Commons](#). You can use facets to inspect the edits on particular items.

Upload edits to Wikibase...

Holotype of *Calibius littoralis* (NZAC04041380).jpg (new item)

File path: /Users/siobhan/Downloads/Training holotype specimens for Leanne/Calibius littoralis_d_HT.jpg
 File name: Holotype of *Calibius littoralis* (NZAC04041380).jpg
 =={{int:filedesc}}==
 {{Information}}
 Wikitext (do not override): =={{int:license-header}}==
 {{License from structured data}}
 [[Category:Type specimens at New Zealand Arthropod Collection]]

Caption (do not override) Holotype specimen of <i>Calibius littoralis</i> (NZAC04041380) held at New Zealand Arthropod Collection (English)	
inception (P571)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2014 1 references
depicts (P180)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Calibius littoralis</i> (Q21248837) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references holotype (Q1061403) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references holotype of <i>Calibius littoralis</i> (Q138044264) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references
creator (P170)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (Q1801980) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references Birgit E. Rhode (Q26269698) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references
source of file (P7482)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> file available on the internet (Q74228490) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> operator (P137) Global Biodiversity Information Facility (Q1531570) described at URL (P973) https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/5294288858 1 references

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

sponsor (P859)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manaaki Whenua – Landcare Research (Q1801980) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> object of statement has role (P3831) digitization sponsor (Q131344184) 1 references
collection (P195)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Zealand Arthropod Collection (Q22111504) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> object of statement has role (P3831) holding collection (Q137935182) 1 references New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science (Q134467046) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> object of statement has role (P3831) holding institution (Q131597993) 1 references
copyright license (P275)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (Q20007257) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references
copyright holder (P3931)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New Zealand Institute for Bioeconomy Science (Q134467046) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references
instance of (P31)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> photograph (Q125191) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references
copyright status (P6216)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> copyrighted (Q50423863) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 references

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once satisfied that there are no issues with the upload and that the preview is accurate the editor can then commence the upload of the image file and its structured data to Wikimedia Commons.

Upload edits to Wikibase

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

The editor should go to the Wikibase extension tab at the top righthand side of the OpenRefine project and choose “Upload edits to Wikibase” from the dropdown menu.

Log In to Wikimedia Commons

Wikimedia Commons account

**WIKIMEDIA
COMMONS**

Logging in to [Wikimedia Commons](#) lets you upload edits directly from OpenRefine.

You are encouraged to login with [bot passwords](#), see this [wiki page](#) to learn how to get one.

Username

Password

Remember me [?](#)

You can also [login with your owner-only consumer](#).

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

OpenRefine will then require the editor to log in to their Wikimedia Commons account with their username and their password.

Add edit summary

Upload edits to Wikimedia Commons

You are about to upload 3 edits to [Wikimedia Commons](#). Please check them carefully. Large edit batches should be submitted for [bot review](#) first.

i

New media uploaded Locate rows

This batch will upload new media files. Please make sure the files you upload are admissible on this wiki.

3

You are logged in as: [Ambrosia10](#).

summary

maxlag Must be a positive integer. Leave this to the default value unless you know [how maxlag works](#).

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once successfully logged in the editor should then add an edit summary for the batch upload about to be undertaken by OpenRefine on behalf of the editor. The editor should then press the “Upload edits” button to commence the upload. Depending on the number and size of the image files the batch may take some time to complete.

3 rows			
Schema Issues 6 Preview			
Show as: rows records Show: 5 10 25 50 100 500 1000 rows			
All	path	filename	caption
	1. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex comans (CHR 691423).png	File:Carex comans (CHR 691423).png Choose new match	specimen of Carex comans held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 691423)
	2. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png	File:Carex sinclairii (CHR 695901).png Choose new match	specimen of Carex sinclairii held at the Allan herbarium (Cedit 695901)
	3. /Users/siobhan/Downloads/CHR Grass sample image upload/Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png	File:Carex dipsacea (CHR 688095).png Choose new match	specimen of Carex dipsacea held at the Allan herbarium (CHR 688095)

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

Once complete the OpenRefine project will show the Wikimedia Commons files after having been uploaded.

Wikibase editing results

Wikibase editing results
https://commons.wikimedia.org/entity/M185776788
https://commons.wikimedia.org/entity/M185776795

Screenshot of OpenRefine Project. Siobhan Leachman. [CC0](#)

OpenRefine will also generate a new column in the project giving the Wikibase editing results.

Helpful resources

- Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400>
- Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikimedia Commons + SDC. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881782>
- Wikimedia Commons uploads : Uploading of images by an employee of the copyright holder. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556>
- OpenRefine's website: <https://www.openrefine.org/>
- Download OpenRefine: <https://openrefine.org/download.html>
- Download and install the Wikimedia Commons extension for OpenRefine: <https://github.com/OpenRefine/CommonsExtension>
- Download and install the File extension for OpenRefine <https://openrefine.org/blog/2025/02/11/FilesExtension>
- General OpenRefine documentation: <https://openrefine.org/docs>
- Wikimedia Commons OpenRefine documentation <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:OpenRefine>
- Wikimedia Foundation “OpenRefine for Wikimedia Commons: the basics” self paced course https://learn.wiki/courses/course-v1:Wikimedia-Foundation+WMF_GLAM001+2023/about
- Youtube presentation on structured data on commons <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dLFRReHgDpWo>
- Linked Open Data Workflow https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Linked_open_data_workflow
- Wikimedia Commons Structured Data modelling https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Structured_data/Modeling
- Wikidata WikiProject Natural History Specimen data model https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Natural_History_Specimen_Data_Model